

Synthesis of some Modified Uracil and Uridine Derivatives

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One of the most distinctive structural features of t_{RNA}, transfer ribonucleic acids, is the presence of significant proportion of post-transcriptional modification of the common nucleosides uridine, adenosine, cytosine and guanosine¹. Nearly all t_{RNA}'s sequences contain modified analogues of uridine at the first position of the anticodon, position 34, their occurrence is accompanied by restriction or amplification of various interactions in the process of protein biosynthesis². The nature and function of the majority of the hypermodified uridine analogues are still unidentified³. In the most reported cases⁴, the hydrogen of the fifth position of pyrimidine ring is replaced by different substituents which may be coplanar or has skew conformation to the pyrimidine ring. The structure of these substituents and also its conformation may have an important influence on its biological activity⁵. Among modified nucleoside derivatives those containing amino acid residues are expected to exhibit promising antimicrobial activities⁶.

In an attempt to understand the function of these modifications and their effect on protein biosynthesis process, the present work was mainly devoted to synthesise some modified uracil and uridine by coupling with different aliphatic and aromatic amino acids to form 5-substituted uracil and uridine. This may serve as the first step towards the synthesis of hypermodified nucleosides similar to those naturally present in t_{RNA}'s sequences.

Results and Discussion

5-Hydroxymethyluracil and 2',3'-O-isopropylidene-5-hydroxymethyl uridine⁷ were obtained by reaction of uracil and protected uridine with paraformaldehyde in alkaline medium. The pure compounds were obtained by stirring with Doxex-5(H⁺)-form (100–200

mesh). 5-Hydroxymethyl derivatives were reacted with different aromatic and aliphatic N-protected amino acids, namely, Boc-Gly, Boc-Ala, Boc-Val, Boc-Pro and Boc-Trp. t-Butyloxycarbonyl group was used as N-terminal protecting group, since its mild cleavage in slightly acidic medium does not damage the uracil ring. The coupling reactions were carried out by using dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (DCC) which is successfully used to promote the esterification reaction between the carboxylic group of the Boc amino acid and the hydroxyl group of 5-hydroxymethyl uracil and uridine via formation of active ester intermediate of the Boc amino acid which enables rapid and quantitative reactions⁸.

Formation of 1a-e : The esterification reactions (Scheme 1) were carried out at room temperature with stirring for 24 h to produce **1a-e** (25–29%) after crystallisation from absolute ethanol : **1a**, m.p. 220–22°; **b** 228–30°; **c**, 218–20°; **d**, 233–35°; **e**, 226–28°; **1a-e**, $\nu_{\max}$ 3 220–3 190 (NH), 1 680–1 675 (C=O), 1 640–1 620 (C=N) and 1 090–1 000 cm⁻¹ (C–O); **1b**, δ (CDCl₃) 1.35 (3H, d, CH₃), 1.41 (9H, s, -O-C(CH₃)₃), 4.3 (1H, q, CH), 4.45 (2H, s, CH₂) and 4.75 (1H, s, ArH); **1d** δ (CDCl₃) 1.32 (9H, s, -O-C(CH₃)₃), 2.2 (2H, m, CH₂), 2.3 (2H, q, CH₂), 2.6 (1H, t, CH), 3.2 (2H, t, CH₂), 4.4 (2H, s, CH₂-O) and 4.7 (1H, s, ArH).

a: Boc-Gly

b: Boc-Ala

c: Boc-Val

d: Boc-Pro

e: Boc-Trp

Scheme 1

The structures were also confirmed by coupling 5-chloromethyluracil⁹ (**2**) instead of 5-hydroxymethyluracil with the same N-protected aliphatic and aromatic amino acids giving the same compounds **1a-e**. The products were found to have identical analytical data and spectral features to those produced by the reaction of 5-hydroxymethyluracil with the same protected amino acids.

Formation of 4a-e : 2',3'-O-Isopropylidene uridine¹⁰ was synthesised via reaction of uridine with anhydrous cupric sulphate and concentrated sulphuric acid in acetone at room temperature. The product was then reacted with paraformaldehyde in alkaline medium to give 2',3'-O-isopropylidene-5-hydroxymethyluridine (**3**) in 85% yield⁷. 2',3'-O-Isopropylidene-5-chloromethyluridine¹¹ (**5**) was formed via treatment of 2',3'-O-hydroxymethyluridine with 15% dry HCl in dioxane solution at 0–5° for 2 h.

Compound **3** was reacted with Boc-Gly, Boc-Ala, Boc-Val, Boc-Pro and Boc-Trp, respectively (Scheme 2). Dicyclohexylcarbodiimide was used to promote esterification reaction carried out at room temperature with stirring for 24 h to produce compounds **4a-e** (30–42%) : **4a**, m.p. 261–63°; **b**, 277–79°; **c**, 286°; **d**, 281–83°; **e**, 291–92°; **4a-e**, $\nu_{\max}$ 3 510–3 400 (OH), 3 240–3 180 (NH), 1 680–1 675 (C=O), 1 645–1 610 (C=N) and 1 095–1 000 cm^{-1} (C–O); **4a** $\delta(\text{CDCl}_3)$ 1.30–1.50 (6H, ds, $(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 1.38 (9H, s, $\text{O-C}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 3.42 (2H, m, H_5), 4.1 (1H, m, H_4), 4.38 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2\text{-N}$), 4.43 (2H, s, $\text{CH}_2\text{-O}$), 5.3 (1H, br s, H_1) and 8.5 (1H, br s, H_6); **4b** $\delta(\text{CDCl}_3)$ 1.32, 1.53 (6H, ds, $\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 1.35 (3H, s, $\text{CH}_3\text{-C}$), 1.39 (9H, s, $-\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 3.4 (2H, m, H_5), 4.0 (1H, m, H_4), 4.20 (1H, q, CH-CH_3), 4.7 (2H, s, CH_2O), 5.78 (1H, br, H_1) and 8.2 (1H, s, H_6).

The structures of **4a-e** were also confirmed by coupling of 5-chloromethyluridine derivative (**5**) instead of **3** with the same N-protected amino acids. The reactions were carried out in absolute ethanol in presence of trimethylamine at 90° to produce compounds **4a-e**. The products were found to have identical analytical and spectral data to those produced by reaction of 5-hydroxymethyluridine (**3**) with the same protected amino acids.

Scheme 2

Experimental

All melting points were recorded on an electrothermal Gallenkamp apparatus and are uncorrected. Microanalysis was carried out in the Microanalytical Laboratory, Faculty of Science, Cairo University. ¹H nmr spectra were carried out on Bruker HFX 90, WP 80, WH 80, WM 400 spectrometer and ir spectra on Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer.

Formation of 1a-e and 4a-e : 5-Hydroxymethyluracil or -uridine (4 mmol) was dissolved in warm DMF (10 ml). Symmetrical anhydride of the N^α-Boc-amino acid was prepared in a separate reaction vessel by adding DCC (4 mmol) to Boc amino acid (8 mmol), namely, Boc-Gly, Boc-Ala, Boc-Val, Boc-Pro and Boc-Trp¹² dissolved in DMF (30 ml). The symmetrical anhydride was filtered upon the 5-hydroxymethyluracil or -uridine solution, then pyridine (0.5 ml) was added. The volume of the mixture was reduced to 10 ml under reduced pressure, stirred for 8–24 h and then left. The resulting white crystals were recrystallised from methanol.

Formation of 1a-e : A mixture of 5-chloromethyluracil or -uridine (0.8 g, 5 mmol), Boc amino acid (5 mmol), namely, Boc-Gly, Boc-Ala, Boc-Val, Boc-Pro and Boc-Trp and triethylamine (0.7 ml) was refluxed in an oil-bath at 90° for 24 h, then the mixture was filtered and cooled. The resulting white crystals were recrystallised from absolute ethanol.

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NOTE

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